

Experimental

All the melting points were determined by capillary method and are uncorrected. The mass spectra of some compounds were recorded on a Jeol JMS-D 300 spectrometer. 3-Mercapto-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles were obtained according to literature methods².

as-Triazino[5,6-*b*]indol-3-ylhydrazines (1): The corresponding 3-mercapto-*as*-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole (0.01 mol) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (10 ml; 98%) with occasional shaking for 1–1.5 h. The resulting solid product was washed with alcohol and dried. The product was recrystallised from aqueous DMF to yield fine pale yellow crystals of 1.

Scheme 1

Similarly, the other hydrazines are prepared: R=H, R'=6,8-dichloro, 80%, m.p. 305–06°; R=H, R'=8-methyl, 75%, m.p. 286–87°; R=methyl, R'=8-chloro, 65%, m.p. 325°; R=ethyl, R'=8-chloro, 65%, m.p. 334–35°; R=methyl, R'=8-methyl, 65%, m.p. 265–66°; R=methyl, R'=6,8-dichloro, 70%, m.p. 258°.

*Nitrofurfuraldehyde as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indol-3-ylhydrazine (2a)*: To a solution of 1a (1.0 g, 0.005 mol) in alcohol (50 ml), nitrofurfural diacetate (1.2 g, 0.005 mol) and concentrated H₂SO₄ (0.5 ml) were added and the contents refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture on removal of alcohol, yielded the corresponding hydrazone. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous DMF to yield the title compound (2a).

Similarly, 2b–j were prepared (Table 1).

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Chemical Constituents of *Spilanthes paniculata*

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IN continuation of our studies on an annual herb of Tripura, *Spilanthes paniculata* Wall. ex DC^{1,2} (Fam: *Compositae*), we now report the isolation and characterisation of stearic acid, tetratriacontanoic acid, sitosterol, stigmasterol and sitosterol-*O*-β-D-glucoside from the aerial parts of the plant.

Aerial parts of the plant collected from Khayerpur (Agartala), were air-dried, milled and extracted (1.0 kg) with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) and 90% ethanol successively in a soxhlet. The petrol extract was concentrated to a residue (6.5 g) and column chromatographed through Si-gel. The residue from the benzene eluate on recolumn chromatography afforded two crystalline compounds, A (0.06 g) and B (0.015 g). The compound A, m.p. 68° (*M*⁺ 284), was identified as stearic acid by its colour reaction with starch-iodide paper, positive bicarbonate test and spectral (ir, ¹H nmr and mass) studies and finally by co-glc of its Me-ester with an authentic Me-sterate in a 10% PEGA column. Compound B, C₃₄H₆₈O₂ (*M*⁺ 508), m.p. 93° gave positive starch-iodide and bicarbonate tests for carboxylic acids; ν_{max} (KBr) 2 920, 2 850, 1 709 (C=O) and 1 460 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) 0.88 (3H, t, Me), 1.24 (62H, br s, 31 CH₂) and 2.32 (2H, t, CH₂ adjacent to C=O); *m/z* (rel. intensity%) 508 [*M*⁺ (12.5), 480 [*M*-28]⁺ (60.0), 452 [*M*-2×28]⁺ (62.5), 424 (40.0), 396 (25.0), 368 (18.0), 340 (7.5), 312 (15.0), 284 (25.0), 256 (37.5), 228 (17.5), 200 (12.5),

172 (22.5), 144 (12.5), 60 (36.0) and 55 (100.0, base peak). All these facts indicate the compound to be tetratriacontanoic acid, $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{32}\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ (lit³, m.p. 98.2°). This appears to be the first report of its isolation from a plant source.

The benzene-chloroform (4 : 1) eluate gave a solid which was homogeneous on tlc. The solid on repeated crystallisation from benzene-chloroform mixture furnished needle shaped crystals (0.05 g), m.p. 132°. It was characterised as a mixture of stigmasterol (66.7%) and sitosterol (33.3%) in the usual manner by its positive Liebermann-Burchard test and comparison of spectral (ir, ¹H nmr and mass) data⁴ and finally co-glc⁵ of its acetate (m.p. 122°) with acetates of the authentic samples.

The alcoholic extract (10.0 g) on column chromatography through Si-gel afforded a homogeneous residue from ethyl acetate-methanol (9 : 1) eluate. The residue on repeated crystallisation from methanolic chloroform solution gave white crystals (0.035 g), m.p. 278–80°. It responded to positive Liebermann-Burchard test and showed ir and ¹H nmr spectra diagnostic⁶ of Δ^5 -sterolglycosides. The FD-ms⁷ of the compound revealed some significant peaks at 599 [$M+\text{Na}$]⁺ (10.9 percent), 577 [$M+\text{H}$]⁺ (20.0), 415 [Aglyc+H]⁺ (41.8), 397 [M -hexose+H]⁺ (100.0), 382 (60.0) and 256 (56.4), suggesting it to be a sitosterol-hexoside. The compound on hydrolysis with 2 N HCl in aqueous-methanol (1 : 1) gave sitosterol and D-glucose. Therefore, the glycoside was characterised as sitosterol- β -D-glucoside; the nature of glycosidic linkage was considered as β -from the coupling constant (6.5 Hz) of anomeric sugar proton at δ 4.72.

The presence of stigmasterol and sitosterol-glucoside was reported earlier⁸ from its sister species, *S. acmella*.

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A New Withanolide Datumetelin from the Leaves of *Datura metel* L.

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A new withanolide datumetelin has been isolated from the fresh leaves of *Datura metel*¹ together with the previously known withanolide daturin². The structure of the new compound was established by spectroscopic data.

The leaves extract of *Datura* species are reported to contain mainly tropane alkaloids³ and some steroidal lactones⁴. Earlier we reported the isolation and characterisation of a tropane alkaloid⁵ and two withanolides^{2,6} from the leaves of *Datura metel*. Some withanolides have also been reported recently^{7,8} from the same plant. In this communication we report the isolation and structure elucidation of one more hitherto unknown withanolide, datumetelin (1) from the fresh undried leaves of *D. metel*.

Compound 1 was obtained as a white crystalline solid which formed rectangular plates on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-methanol (9 : 1), m.p. 180–82°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 56^\circ$ (*c* 0.12 CHCl_3) having molecular formula $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_8$ (high resolution mass M^+ 468.2881); λ_{max} 210 nm (α, β -unsaturated ketone); ν_{max} 1685 (α, β -unsaturated carbonyl) and 1712 cm^{-1} (γ -lactone) characteristic of withanolides⁹. Apart from the molecular ion, mass spectra showed intense peaks at 437.2698 ($\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{37}\text{O}_4$) and 436.2618 ($\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{35}\text{O}_4$) resulting from the loss of methoxy group and methanol, respectively. A peak at *m/e* 365.2480 ($\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{35}\text{O}_2$) appeared by the loss of C-25 to C-27 along with their oxygen functions. The cleavage of D/E ring (C-17/20) gave peaks at *m/e* 269.1832 ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}$) and 268.1822 ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}$), with or without transfer of hydrogen. The ¹H nmr spectra exhibited two doublets of double doublets at δ 5.85 (1H, $J_{2,3}$ 10.1, $J_{2,4a}$ 2.9, $J_{2,4b}$ 1.1 Hz), 6.78 (1H, $J_{3,2}$ 10.1, $J_{3,4a}$ 4.9, $J_{3,4b}$ 2.5 Hz) and a doublet of triplet at δ 5.55 (1H, J 6.0 Hz) due to the olefinic protons H-2, H-3 and H-6, respectively. Three sharp singlets related to the methyl groups appeared at δ 0.67 (H-18), 1.22 (H-19) and 1.31 (H-28). The signals of H-27a and H-27b appeared as double doublets at δ 3.75 ($J_{27a,27b}$ 9.8, $J_{27a,28}$ 2.8 Hz) and 3.98 ($J_{27b,27a}$ 9.8, $J_{27b,28}$ 7.5 Hz). Whereas the H-25 resonated as double doublet ($J_{25,27a}$ 2.8, $J_{25,27b}$ 7.5 Hz) at δ 2.48.